

ULTIMATE Project Toolkit for Robotic AI-based Data Analysis and Visualization

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Abstract. Different visualisation solutions exist in the literature that allow for advanced analysis of structured data and the development of interactive dashboards. For example, there are various tools for robotics applications and general-purpose data visualisation software solutions. However, these tools do not always allow one to address the advanced needs related to robotic data analytics. In particular, we argue that the existing solutions for robotic applications heavily focus on sensor data diagnosis and debugging. As a result, they do not provide flexible ways to allow the data scientist to integrate AI algorithms. Therefore, in this paper, we propose a novel toolkit architecture that leverages modern web technologies in the process of robotic data inspection, visualisation, and analysis.

Keywords: Robotics · Trustworthy AI-toolkit · Data analysis · Visualization

1 Introduction and Context

As automation continues to grow in various industries, we will likely see more instances of human-robot collaboration. It gradually becomes omnipresent and starts to play a pivotal role in various applications. In such cases, assuring the safety of the human operator becomes a fundamental requirement when designing and developing human-robot collaboration systems. Researchers often distinguish [10] between human-robot interaction (HRI) and Human-robot collaboration (HRC). The HRI considers interactivity between humans and robots, while HRC is focused on humans and robots working together to achieve a common goal.

The purpose of this paper is to propose a toolkit for data analytics and visualisation of temporal, spatial, and spatiotemporal contents (e.g., robot position

and odometry measurements and human pose estimation [16, 15]) in the context of industrial/workshop robot applications. These use cases are a part of the European Commission-funded ULTIMATE project [2]. The main requirements for the toolkit are the ability to access the raw data directly via the web browser, apply AI (data-driven model) algorithms on the data used in the robotics, visualise time-series datasets and generate plots and graphs for the visualisation of temporal data streams. In addition, the toolkit should check the data quality (e.g., synchronisation of temporal data, redundancy), analyse scene structure (e.g., absolute/relative distances between objects) and hypostatise the methods and metrics for anomaly detection (e.g., check if the distance to the robot arm is distinctive enough for crash detection). We also consider features allowing for inspection of what method can be used for certain tasks (e.g., which algorithm for pose estimation) and which and where specific methods for human pose estimation are failing.

The major contribution of this paper is the new AI-based data analysis and visualization toolkit dedicated for analysts and data scientists involved in robotic scenarios.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: other relevant solutions are shortly presented and discussed in Section 2. The proposed architecture of the ULTIMATE visualization toolkit is presented in detail in Section 3. Validation, results and conclusions are given thereafter.

2 Overview of other relevant visualization solutions

In the literature, many different visualisation solutions that allow for advanced analysis of structured data and the development of interactive dashboards have been reported. For example, there is a variety of tools for robotics applications as well as general-purpose data visualisation software solutions. However, these tools do not allow us to address our needs related to analytics. Therefore, in this section, we identify the most popular solutions and explain their limitations. From the analysis of literature and the software repositories of existing solutions for robotics applications, one may notice that there is a great variety of toolkits such as RVIZ⁷, Foxglove Studio⁸, and WebViz⁹. All of them allow the user to combine sensor data (e.g., radar, odometry, images/videos) into a single view in the 3D visualisation environment. It enables basic analysis (or debugging/diagnosis capabilities) of how the robot perceives the world via its sensors. These tools are also quite modular and allow the operator to customise the layouts and the dashboards. In particular, WebViz and Foxglove Studio provide various visualisation components (e.g., for ROS bag, images, point clouds, depths maps visualisation) built on modern JavaScript libraries (e.g., React.js¹⁰,

⁷ Rviz package documentation: <http://wiki.ros.org/rviz>

⁸ Foxglove Website: <https://foxglove.dev/>

⁹ Webviz Website: <https://webviz.io/>

¹⁰ React library documentation: <https://react.dev/>

Regl.js¹¹, Three.js¹²). In that regard, RVIZ looks less flexible as a desktop tool. In particular, it requires the ROS environment to be pre-installed. This eventually limits the user to the Ubuntu operating system (the support for other operating systems is experimental at the moment of writing this paper [9]). Although the installation process is straightforward, it is time-consuming when compared to Foxglove Studio or WebViz, which also support quick and handy docker-based deployment. Moreover, the RViz is quite tightly coupled with other ROS tools and packages, which may not always be required in the basic inspection of ROS bag files. This problem is well addressed by WebViz, where the separation from the ROS toolkit has been achieved thanks to the rosbag.js library [5]. It is a browser-compatible module that allows the user to read ROS bag binary data files without any additional software dependencies.

Apart from dedicated visualisation solutions for robotics applications, there exist general-purpose tools for data analysis and interactive dashboard development such as Grafana¹³ and Kibana¹⁴. Kibana offers means for the presentation of data provided by the Elasticsearch engine in the form of customisable visualisations and saved queries. Kibana also provides numerous options for displaying data in a wide variety of formats, including different charts and graphs, heatmaps, map-based visualisations, etc. Kibana is an integrated product, and it depends on other services from the Elastic Stack¹⁵ (e.g., Elasticsearch database). Grafana is an open-source solution for data analytics via a set of metrics and customizable dashboards, which can include several visualisation options such as geo maps, heat maps, histograms, and a variety of charts and graphs. Grafana is compatible and can connect with numerous data sources, such as Elasticsearch, MySQL, PostgreSQL, Graphite, and others.

Apart from Grafana and Kibana, there is also a variety of other tools (e.g., Tableau¹⁶) that allow building business intelligence on top of raw data. However, in most of the cases, robotics is not the core use case and requires additional software components (e.g., dedicated ETL toolchain [1]) to be set up. These usually facilitate an intermediate data processing step, where the contents of ROS bag files are transformed into a structured database, which can finally be consumed by the visualisation dashboard.

When analysing the literature related to human-robot collaboration (HRC) applications, safety [4] is still a significant challenge when designing and deploying HRC systems. In early works [13] on HRC, researchers pointed out the need for dynamic adaptation of the robotic system to human partners. Following this line of research, we may identify various solutions that rely heavily on accurate human pose estimation [11, 3, 12].

¹¹ Regl project at github: <https://github.com/regl-project/regl>

¹² Three.js Website: https://threejs.org/examples/#webgl_animation_keyframes

¹³ Grafana Website: <https://grafana.com/>

¹⁴ Kibana Website: <https://www.elastic.co/kibana>

¹⁵ Elastic Website: <https://www.elastic.co/elastic-stack/>

¹⁶ Tableau Website: <https://www.cognitiveconvergence.com/tableau.html>

3 Proposed architecture of the ULTIMATE visualization toolkit

3.1 Design rationale

Our analysis shows that the datasets vastly differ from each other from the perspective of format, structure, type, labels and modalities. This constitutes quite a challenge for a universal no-code visualisation toolkit. Moreover, the analysis of existing solutions described in the previous section, shows that the general-purpose visualisation toolkits require rigid data formats that meet the requirements of the specific databases. We also argue that the existing solutions for robotic applications (e.g., RViz, Foxglove Studio) heavily focus on sensor data diagnosis and debugging. As a result, they do not provide flexible ways that will allow the data scientist to integrate AI algorithms. Moreover, to add additional information on top of existing ROS bag files, one has to publish specifically formatted messages to ROS topics. This way it is possible to create 3D scenes from primitive shapes, grids, point clouds, and other renderables. However, this requires other tools or dedicated algorithms inside the existing pipelines, which will provide such data at a source.

Therefore, we decided to treat the ROS bag as raw data to our data analytics algorithms rather than adjusting our processing pipeline and solutions to 3rd party tools like Foxglove or WebViz.

During the analysis of existing solutions, we identified the need for web-based solutions that will allow us to easily combine robotic data with highly customisable ML algorithms for advanced analytics and (later during the project lifetime) for the development of hybrid AI applications. In that regard, JupyterLab¹⁷ looked to us as a bridge that could connect both sides to bring sufficient user experience from both perspectives, namely: data scientist and robotics engineer. JupyterLab facilitates a web-based interactive development environment which (in our opinion) allows for achieving enough flexibility for visualisation and analysis of various types and data formats. Therefore, we made the following design decisions:

- We utilise cloud infrastructure and remote access to the datasets, so that the user is not required to install any dedicated software.
- Python (and dedicated libraries/packages like rosbags¹⁸) are used to read/analyse various samples of data formats.
- JupyterLab/Notebook is used to interact, preprocess, and visualise samples/portions of data.
- (when/if needed) Mercury tool [8] is used to create interactive dashboards.

3.2 Architecture overview

The overview of the proposed architecture has been presented in Fig. 1. The user accesses the infrastructure via a secure SSH tunnel and interacts with the visu-

¹⁷ Jupyter Website: <https://jupyter.org>

¹⁸ <https://pypi.org/project/rosbags/>

alisation using the web browser. The NGINX¹⁹ server is used as a reverse proxy for Jupyter Notebook and static files serving. The Jupyter Kernels facilitate the key functionalities of the visualisation toolkit and provide an environment for interactive computing in Python. These are the processes that run independently, interact with the Jupyter Server (e.g., web user interfaces) and execute code contained in the notebook document.

Fig. 1. Overview of the toolkit architecture. The key functionalities are realised by the Kernels, which handle the user requests, and provide various visualisations via the (Jupyter) Notebook Server.

For the purpose of the visualisation toolkit, we have created several Notebook documents the user can interact with. These facilitate various functionalities, such as:

- Raw data loading,
- Data format parsing (e.g., ROS point cloud),
- Visualisation of temporal, spatial, and spatio-temporal contents (e.g., robot position and odometry measurements),
- Transformation of data format (e.g., from ROS bag file topic to mp4 video),
- Data analytics (e.g., human detection, pose extraction, etc.).

During the interaction with the notebook, the results (e.g., point clouds, human poses) can be stored in a persistent way on the hard drive and used for further processing by another notebook.

3.3 Web-based interactive visualisation

The interaction with the Jupyter documents has been organised into three stages. First, the user selects the use case. The example of a landing page facilitating this

¹⁹ NGINX Website: <https://www.nginx.com/>

step is shown. This allows us to organise the navigation throughout the various Jupyter documents in a more consistent way. Moreover, the various datasets are essentially different, therefore, the notebooks vary significantly. When the user selects the specific use case, the list of available actions (implemented by Jupyter documents) appears.

Finally, when the user picks a specific item on the list, the Jupyter Notebook is presented to the user. Fig. 2 illustrates an example of human pose estimation. In all the notebooks, the same document flow is kept, namely: data processing (e.g., in a frame-by-frame manner), visualisation preparation, and visualisation demonstration.

Fig. 2. Example of the process-build-interact information flow used in the prepared Jupyter documents.

4 Validation

4.1 Dataset content inspection

The first step starts with the basic analysis of the dataset's content. The complexity at that point may vary. In that case, using the list of topics with their types can be useful to quickly identify the most relevant ones. For example, a user may start with the inspection of the video frames and the corresponding depth measurements. It can be particularly useful to identify common fields of view for the cameras, the occlusions appearing due to the robot arm movements, and discontinuities in the depth maps (see Fig. 3). All these aspects are crucial

to understanding what kind of algorithms can be used to identify the human, the robot, and their spatiotemporal relation.

Fig. 3. Examples of depth maps obtained from the experimental environments.

However, the most efficient way to visualise the complex interdependencies between different modalities is to use the Foxglove Studio component, which were made available from the Jupyter notebook. The user simply points to the location of *.bag file and calls the foxglove wrapper function.

In some cases, we found the Foxglove Studio difficult to comprehend the transformations obtained from /tf and /tf_static topics. In such cases, the user may easily access these topics directly and use our wrappers to visualise these in the form of a tree. For example, the static and dynamic trees allowed us to quickly identify which transformation frame is related to the robot's position in 2D space. From that point is quite straightforward to visualise the robot path using the matplotlib package as presented in Fig. 4.

4.2 Format conversion

As already mentioned, there exist sophisticated tools allowing the user to work with the ROS bag files. However, accessing bag files in a random access manner (particularly over the network) is time-consuming. Therefore, in some cases, it could be useful to extract a particular ROS topic and transform it to a more convenient form (e.g., MP4 video or point cloud in a PCD format).

With only a few lines of code, a user may record the video from the ROS messages and quickly preview the content online. Similarly, point clouds require a lot of bandwidth. A single frame has almost 1 million points and it takes some

Fig. 4. Dynamic tree visualising transformation hierarchy.

time to preview it. Therefore, we prepared a dedicated tool, which allows the user to extract point clouds from the ROS bag topic, down-sample them, and inspect them in the Notebook document.

Moreover, direct access to point clouds in the Jupyter environment allows the user to draw additional 3D primitives based on the acquired data.

In the example presented in Fig. 5, the camera information (green box on the left) was used to estimate the human head position in 3D (green box on the right). In that case, we used a face detector which utilises 2D images.

4.3 Data analytics

In contrast to the existing ROS bag visualisation tools, Jupyter Notebook allows for advanced data analytics using various ML/AI frameworks (e.g., PyTorch). In this section, we illustrate how the prepared Jupyter documents can be used by the user to examine various hypotheses regarding the collected data and the possible algorithms that can be used to solve some of the computer vision challenges. Here we particularly focus on the human-robot collaboration. Some of the questions we may ask at this point could be the following:

- Where are (in 3D space) the human operator and the robot arm?
- What part of the collaboration process is happening now?
- What are the spatio-temporal relations between humans and the robot?

Fig. 5. Additional 3D primitives drawn in the Jupyter.

In the prepared notebook, we first created a data processing loop, which analyses one of the videos (the one where the human operator is visible) and extracts the 2D coordinates of human body parts (e.g., head, arms, wrists, etc.). The result is stored as a video stream for further visual inspection. In the Fig. 6, we illustrate the 2D human pose detection. In the considered examples, we applied PoseNet model [6]. It can be noticed that the algorithm fails to correctly point to human body parts' location (e.g., the occluded left hand and leg) when the operator is behind the robot arm.

Fig. 6. Example of 2D pose detection.

Nonetheless, the user may continue with the analysis and try to regress the 3D pose of the human operator on the image. The result for that step is shown in the figure below. However, the discontinuities in the depth maps cause significant

distortions in the measurements and correct estimation of the operator’s pose in 3D space.

In order to improve the pose estimation, we also investigated the adoption of single-view regression estimation methods (e.g., ROMP model [14], which internally uses SMPL model [7] for parametric human body representation). However, we believe that algorithms for multiple views scene perception and pose regression networks (e.g., [17]) will be better suited for human activity recognition.

4.4 Interactive dashboards

Using the Mercury open-source project²⁰, it is also possible to provide interactive dashboards, which do not contain Python code. As it is shown in the figure below, additional elements called widgets are added to the Jupyter document. In that case, the slider controls the frame number value which is further used to load and display adequate visualisation. Using this approach, we created two applications. The first one allows the user to briefly inspect the bag file contents and their topics. The example is shown in the figure below. The second application lets the user examine spatiotemporal relations between images, depths map, and the point clouds. This has been demonstrated in Fig. 7.

4.5 Outcomes from the data models visualisation

From the analysis of the datasets, conclusions were drawn which helped further improve the recorded human-robot collaboration process. First, we noticed that the existing cameras could have a wider field of view, so that the human operator could be recorded by both cameras. Another solution could be to add additional cameras in the WS area. This would significantly help in dealing with the occlusions. Depth maps are essential to visualise the environment as the point clouds. Moreover, we believe that algorithms for multiple views scene perception and pose regression networks, for more accurate 3D human pose estimation, should be further investigated.

5 Conclusions

In this paper, we proposed a novel toolkit for data analytics and visualisation of temporal, spatial, and spatiotemporal contents (e.g., robot position and odometry measurements) dedicated for industrial/workshop robot applications. We particularly focused on the human-robot collaboration from the perspective of anomaly detection in the observed process. Therefore, we proposed methods that allow the analyst to identify 3D spatial details of the position and mutual orientations both of robot and human.

Our future work is now dedicated to further tests in complex scenarios and use-cases specified within the ULTIMATE project.

²⁰ Mercury Website: <https://runmercury.com/>

Fig. 7. Analysis of spatiotemporal relations between, images, depths map, and the point clouds using Mercury tool.

Acknowledgements. This work is funded under the ULTIMATE project, which has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101070162.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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